

Hintergrund: Little is known about sexual minorities' preferences regarding long-term care and how these differ from those of heterosexuals.

Zielsetzung: The purpose of this study was to investigate the preferences for long-term care services among heterosexuals and sexual minority individuals.

Methode: Data from a large nationally representative survey "*Health care research in old age: sexual orientation and long-term care preferences in Germany*" conducted in December 2021 were used. Altogether n=4,000 individuals aged 40-70 participated. The average age was 55.0 years, 49.8% were female. Preferences for the following five long-term care settings were assessed: own home, home of relatives, assisted living, nursing home, and care abroad. Further, we analysed preferred type of homecare namely informal caregivers, professional home care services, mix of both, and round-the-clock caregiver from abroad. Individuals rated each long-term care option on a 4-point Likert scale from 1-strongly disagree, 2-rather disagree, 3 - rather agree to 4 - strongly agree. For the analysis we used dichotomized answers (agree; disagree). Covariates included e.g., age, sex, habitation situation, self-rated-health, presence of children, and social network. To assess the differences in preferences we used Firth logistic regression models.

Ergebnisse: Altogether, data on sexual orientation were available for 3,951 (98.8%) individuals. In our sample, 3,618 (91.6%) individuals were heterosexual, 195 (4.9%) were homosexual and 138 (3.5%) were bisexual.

Overall, *regardless of sexual orientation*, 89.2% of individuals preferred being cared at their own home, 59.4% considered moving to assisted living facilities, and 26.2% to a nursing home. More homosexuals and bisexuals (17.6% and 16.3%) preferred care abroad than heterosexuals (12.1%; $p < 0.05$). *Home care:* mix of professional home care and informal care was the most preferred option (77.3%), followed by a professional home care (71.1%) and informal care (53.3%).

In a further step, we adjusted the analysis for, among other things, the socio-demographic and health-related covariates. In the adjusted analysis, the differences in preferences with regard to sexual orientation among *all* analysed outcomes were no longer significant.

Implikation für Versorgungspraxis: Our results revealed that preferences for care settings (e.g., own home, nursing home) and preferences for type of care (e.g., informal care, professional home care) did not differ significantly between heterosexuals, homosexuals and bisexuals. We showed that participants' health, age, gender, living situation, whether they had children and social network had a greater influence on long-term care preferences than sexual orientation. Our findings suggests that the development and expansion of professional home care services adapted to the needs of both heterosexual and sexual minority individuals may be the optimal long-term care policy solution.